

Study on the dielectric behaviour of magnesium ammonium phosphate hexahydrate pellets in room temperature

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Abstract : The struvite or Magnesium Ammonium Phosphate Hexahydrate (MAPH) crystals are one among the most prominent and highly occurring urinary stone crystals. These stones are mainly occurring in human due to urinary tract infections. The struvite crystals were grown *in vitro* by single diffusion gel growth technique using silica gel as a medium. The grown crystals were given for XRD characterization to confirm its crystalline nature. The grown crystals were made into pellets and underwent dielectric study. The dielectric property of pellets at room temperature with variation in frequency was studied. The result shows a noticeable variation in the dielectric behaviour of the material as frequency varies.

Keywords : MAPH, struvite, dielectric property, urinary stone.

Introduction

Magnesium Ammonium Phosphate Hexahydrate (MAPH) or struvite stone are the most prominently found infectious urinary stone type¹ which are more commonly found in women². It is formed in human body due to the presence of urea splitting bacteria in urinary tract and growth of this stone type is promoted by the alkaline urine condition³⁻⁵. It is very commonly found in Asian and African continents⁶. The gel growth technique is the most effective method for growing biological crystals *in vitro*. The gel growth technique is mainly of two types namely single diffusion and double diffusion technique. The struvite crystals are developed *in vitro* using single diffusion gel technique which is the most simple *in vitro* model⁷. The gel growth technique will mimic the same biological reaction which happens inside the body and will maintain the same environment for the reaction to occur^{8,9}. The developed crystals were given for various characterizations like XRD, dielectric study. This study mainly concentrates on the dielectric behaviour of the crystals in room temperature as varies frequency is applied. As the frequency varies the material will drastically change its property from insulator to conductor¹⁰.

Experimental

Materials required :

Sodium meta silicate (Sigma-Aldrich), ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (Sigma-Aldrich), magnesium acetate (Sigma-Aldrich), double distilled water.

Growth of crystal :

The struvite crystals were developed using single diffusion gel growth technique. In this method, the matrix gel is prepared by mixing sodium meta silicate solution of density 1.03 g cm⁻³ with 0.5 M of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate solution by adjusting the pH 7.2⁵. The solution was poured into the test tube and kept for gelling. After 48 h, the gel has been set and 1 M of magnesium acetate solution is added. This act as a supernatant solution and it penetrates through the gel and react with the chemical to form struvite crystals as given in the equation below,

Preparation of pellets :

The crystals formed in the gel were removed and smashed into powder using motor. The well grinded par-

ticles are made into pellets of uniform size and shape. The pellets used here for study are of thickness 2×10^{-3} m and area 1.326×10^{-4} m².

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) characterization :

In order to confirm the crystalline nature and crystal type, the developed crystal was given for XRD characterization. The characterization was done with the instrument PANalytical Model X'pert PRO X-ray diffractometer with CuK α radiation (of wave length 1.54060 Å).

Dielectric study on pellets :

The developed pellets were coated with silver paste on its both sides and were given for dielectric study. This study was done with the help of the instrument N4L PSM-1735 Impedance Analyser. The temperature was set for 300 °C which was the current room temperature and the frequency range has given from 1 KHz–1 MHz.

Results and discussion

The XRD of the sample crystal is obtained as shown in Fig. 1. The result graph is analysed with standard JCPDS-96-900-7675 value and the struvite type is confirmed.

Fig. 1. Powder XRD pattern for struvite crystals.

The dielectric constant is calculated with their varying capacitance value by using the standard equation¹¹. The dielectric constant variation with frequency is plotted in Fig. 2.

$$\text{Dielectric constant, } K = C_p * [t / (A * \epsilon_0)] \quad (1)$$

The dielectric constant of the sample will be high for low

Fig. 2. Variation of dielectric constant with frequency.

frequency. As the frequency increases the dielectric constant will decrease and is observed that drastic drop down of dielectric constant will occur for higher frequencies. The high dielectric constant shows the materials high polarizing state and the material will be in slightly conducting state due to shift of positive ions in the material. For higher frequencies, the dielectric constant will decrease which shows that the polarizing ability of the material gradually decreases and the material slowly decreases its conducting capacity.

The dielectric loss (tan D) variation for different frequencies at room temperature is plotted in Fig. 3. Dielectric loss is a unit less quantity which shows the amount of energy dissipated by the material when it is applied by

Fig. 3. Variation of dielectric loss with frequency.

Fig. 4. The variation of (a) resistivity (ρ_{ac}) and (b) conductivity (σ_{ac}) with frequencies.

external field. The dielectric loss will be high at low frequency and as frequency increases the dielectric loss will decrease. The dielectric constant is high during low frequency which shows that the material will be in slightly conducting nature hence the loss of energy will be high. The material turn to be an insulator when the frequency increases, hence the dielectric loss will be reduced.

The ac resistivity (ρ_{ac}) and ac conductivity (σ_{ac}) were calculated using the below given equations¹²,

$$\rho_{ac} = [2\pi f C t] / A \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{ac} = 1/\rho_{ac} \quad (3)$$

The Fig. 4 shows the variation of ac resistivity and ac conductivity with frequencies applied at room temperature. The material will act as a conductor in its low frequency region. Hence the resistivity will be low and conductivity will be high in low frequencies. As the frequency increases, the material's conducting property decreases and thereby the resistivity will shoot up as shown in Fig. 4.

Conclusion

The struvite crystals were developed *in vitro* and its dielectric property study has been done. It was observed that the same material can act as conductor as well as inductor according to the external frequency applied. The struvite material can be polarized in low frequency hence can act as a good dielectric material. Hence struvite can be used to manufacture capacitors and dielectric resona-

tors. In treatment background, the lithotripsy treatment will be more efficient if the material will be in high dielectric state. Hence lower frequency range will be the proper for the treatment for smashing struvite stones.

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